

THESIS

**STUDY OF CLINICAL PROFILE OF MULTITRANSFUSED
THALASSEMIA PATIENTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
THYROID AND LIVER FUNCTION**

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INTRODUCTION

Cooley & Lee first described a form of severe anemia occurring early in life and associated with splenomegaly and bone changes in 1925. This anemia is also known as Cooley's anemia. It was Whipple who coined the term "Thalassemia" noting occurrence of the disease in mediterranean region in early years ¹. The term "Thalassemia" is derived from Greek word "Thalassa" which means "the sea".

Thalassemia is a recessively inherited heterogenous group of disorder. It results from inability of the patient's red cells to synthesize an adequate amount of either α or β chain in the hemoglobin molecule. Accordingly the condition is broadly divided into α or β thalassemia. The β thalassemia has emerged as a huge public health problem worldwide ². It occurs in high frequency in a broad belt extending from mediterranean basin through the Middle East, Indian subcontinent, Burma & Southeast Asia ³.

It has been estimated that in India nearly 8000-10000 new thalassemia [homozygous] cases are born every year. The β thalassemia gene is more commonly found in the *Punjabis, Sindhis, Bengalis & Gujratis* ⁴.

The affected children are well after birth. Anemia usually develops during first few months of life and become progressively severe. The infant fails to thrive and may have feeding problems. The course of the disease in the childhood depends almost entirely on whether the child is maintained on adequate transfusion program. The classic textbook picture of Cooley's anemia describes the disease as it was seen before the children could be maintained on regular blood transfusion. If adequate transfusion is possible affected children grow and develop normally and have minimum abnormal physical sign. The disease poses a great problem due to the effects of iron loading resulting from ineffective erythropoiesis

and repeated blood transfusion. Inadequately transfused child develops typical features of Cooley's anemia. Stunted growth with bossing of skull, overgrowth of maxillary region and face gradually assuming Mongoloid appearance³.

Management of thalassemia patients changed a lot with advancement in medical science. Patients have increased life expectancy and better quality of life with hypertransfusion therapy⁵ which maintains the hemoglobin level at minimum baseline level [12 gm%]. Hypertransfusion invariably leads to hemosiderosis because each 500-ml of blood delivers 200 mg of iron that can't be excreted by physiological means⁶. Children who have grown and developed normally throughout first 10 years of life as a result of regular blood transfusion begin to develop the symptoms of iron overload as they enter puberty. First indication of iron overload is usually the absence of pubertal growth spurt and failure of menarche. In Indian children the main problem is failure to maintain adequate Hemoglobin level due to inadequate transfusion. In addition facilities for removal of excess iron by regular chelation therapy is neither widely available nor affordable by the unfortunate parents. This transfusional hemosiderosis have detrimental outcome in form of hyperpigmentation, hepatic fibrosis & cirrhosis, growth failure, delayed puberty and endocrinenopathies namely diabetes mellitus, hypogonadism, hypoparathyroidism, hypothyroidism⁷. Growth retardation seen in thalassemia patients is a consequence of severe anemia and low somatomedin activity. Somatomedin synthesis is reduced due to hepatic hemosiderosis¹

Hepatic enlargement in early life is related to extramedullary hematopoiesis. In later life hepatomegaly is caused by extensive cirrhosis with nodular aggregate of regenerating hepatocytes as a result of deposition of iron in Kuffer cell & hepatocytes¹. In patients who are regularly transfused to maintain adequate hemoglobin level cardiopulmonary complications are uncommon in first decade of

life. In second decade the patients face the consequence of myocardial hemosiderosis, the leading cause of death in these patients. Congestive heart failure and arrhythmias may be noted as early as 6 years of age but usually these conditions do not have their onset until midpoint of second decade of life in adequately transfused patients. In developing countries like India heart failure is very common due to severe anemia due to inadequate blood transfusion.

Endocrine organs bear a heavy burden of iron overload in thalassemia patients. The hypothalamico-pituitary thyroid axis is very sensitive to iron mediated damage. Thyroxine reserve is also reduced in multitransfused thalassemia patients ¹. Presence of hypothyroidism had been documented in a number of studies, which is mainly subclinical in nature, ^{1,15, 18 19,20,21,31, 54}. Iron deposition had been implicated as a cause of hypothyroidism. Some studies did not found any significant thyroid dysfunction ^{23, 27,29,30}. In addition to the iron overload persistent and prolonged anoxia due to anemia is another important contributory factor for endocrine dysfunction. Detection of hypothyroidism is of great clinical significance. Hypothyroidism can itself cause growth failure, which can add to the existing growth retardation in thalassemia patients. An effective and cheap replacement therapy in form of 'thyroxine' is available for hypothyroidism. Thyroxine replacement can halt the growth retardation caused by hypothyroidism. This study is meant to find out effect of multiple blood transfusion in thalassemia patients on growth and evaluation of hepatic and thyroid function.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- ❖ Clinical examination of thalassemia patients to find out effect disease on their growth, thyroid and liver function.
- ❖ Bio chemical evaluation of liver & thyroid function and correlation with clinical finding.
- ❖ Study of iron overload by estimation of serum ferritin and its implication in thyroid and liver function.
- ❖ To find out the extent of thyroid and liver dysfunction.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Thalassemia infants are born normally. The clinical expression of β thalassemia major commences at several months of age when the weaning synthesis of hemoglobin F is normally offset by rising production of hemoglobin A. Marked expansion of bone marrow occurs in thalassemia to compensate the worsening anemia resulting out of premature destruction of damaged red blood cells. A thalassemia child commonly presents with anemia and failure to thrive in later half of infancy. This children also show characteristics bony changes. Hepatosplenomegaly is very common and rarely high rates of hemolysis leads to jaundice ^{7,11}.

The last century had observed a revolutionary approach in management of thalassemia patients. The conventional management of thalassemia is based on a program of regular blood transfusion and iron chelation. This has changed thalassemia from a invariably fatal disease into a chronic disease permitting a normal life or at least prolonged survival with evidences of bone changes due to marrow expansion, failure to thrive and other hypoxic complications ¹². With hypertransfusion therapy most patients with thalassemia are free of complication of anemia and compensatory bone marrow expansion.

200 mg of iron get deposited in tissue from each 500 ml of blood transfusion. This iron couldn't be removed from the body by physiological means⁶. Mammals don't have an excretory system of iron that helps to conserve iron. This phenomenon has its ill effects for people who hyper absorb iron or iatrogenically receive excessive amount of iron parenterally or through hypertransfusion ⁷. Normally iron is stored in the form of ferritin, a protein. The synthesis of ferritin is influenced by influx of iron. When the storage capacity of ferritin exceeds, pathological amount of metabolically active iron is released intracellularly as partially degraded ferritin-hemosiderin & free iron. This iron produces 'Hydroxy radicals' by

catalyzing lipidperoxidation in cellular organelle like mitochondria, lysosome, sarcoplasmic reticulum. The hydroxy radical causes cell death and eventually organ failure ¹².

Normally plasma iron is bound to iron binding protein transferrin. The iron binding capacity of transferrin is adequate for a limited amount of iron load. In thalassemia major the plasma is full with catabolic RBC iron which exceeds the binding capacity of transferrin. The resultant effect is the emergence of toxic non-transferrin bound iron [NTBI] in the plasma. The NTBI by virtue of its capability to get deposited in tissues at a rate 200 times greater than transferrin bound iron. The principal target organs for this iron toxicity are heart, liver and endocrine organs ¹³. The iron overload is tested biochemically by estimating serum ferritin. Under steady state condition serum ferritin level correlates with total body iron store thus making serum ferritin as the most convenient lab test to estimate iron store ¹⁴.

Physical growth is markedly reduced in thalassemia ¹¹. The decrease in height & weight is greater in adolescent years than early years and growth spurt is delayed. This growth failure has been attributed to chronic hypoxia, increased energy demand by enhanced erythropoiesis and associated malnutrition. The growth failure is very common in spite of maintaining hemoglobin towards normal. The [Growth Hormone]GH-& [Insulin Like Growth Factor] IGF system probably does not have an important role in the growth failure in Multitransfused thalassemia patients ¹⁵. Reduced level of somatomedin caused by decreased hepatic synthesis has been linked with growth failure ¹.

Clinically thalassemia patients have moderate to severe degree of pallor. The hemoglobin level is usually between 2-6 gm/dl without transfusion. Mild icteric tinge in the sclera may be seen rarely. Serum bilirubin level is moderately elevated between 1-3 mg/dl. This bilirubin level depends on the rate of hemolysis activity,

mass of hemoglobin available for hemolysis and functional capacity of liver to excrete the bilirubin ¹¹.

Gangeni B et al ¹⁶ in 1986 studied 74 patients of β thalassemia major and found transaminase level three times normal for over three months. They found a direct relationship between the elevated transaminase level and age of thalassemia patients, ferritin level iron over load. On liver histology they demonstrated siderosis, fibrosis, chronic inflammatory infiltration & vacuolar degeneration.

The development of chronic liver disease is also supported by De santis et al¹⁷. They studied 29 patients with thalassemia major who had received intensive chelation for between 6.2-8.8 years. 22 of the 29 cases had normal liver function test before chelation therapy introduced. At the end of the study they found chronic active hepatitis [11case] chiefly due to hepatitis B infection, cirrhosis of liver [8cases] & normal liver function [10 cases] in their study in thalassemia patients. The patients also had impaired glucose tolerance [11 cases] and frank diabetes [6case]. They stressed on more intensive chelation therapy to prevent iron mediated tissue damage.

In thalassemia endocrinopathies results from chronic transfusion & accompanying hemosiderosis. Madeddu G et al ¹⁸ studied growth rate, thyroid function & skeletal maturation in 50 thalassemic children [age 2-13 years] and 50 controls [matched for age and sex that were not anemic]. They found growth retardation in thalassemia patients. The retardation presents during first year of life and affected almost all the subjects when they reached puberty. Discrepancy between bone & height age in-patients was not significantly different from controls. They showed \downarrow T₃, \downarrow T₄ & \uparrow TSH indicative of hypothyroidism. This hypothyroidism, already present in early life did not worsen with increasing age. They expressed that in β thalassemia hypothyroidism could not be the cause of retarded growth since they had not found any correlation

between severity of growth retardation and impairment of thyroid function.

Cavallo L et al ¹⁹ investigated thyroid function by a TRH [Thyroid Releasing Hormone] test in 24 clinically prepubertal children [3-15 years old] with β thalassemia major. They determined basal serum T₃, T₄, TBG [Thyroid Binding Globulin], TSH, & TSH during TRH stimulation and correlated it with age and serum ferritin level. They showed low basal serum T₃, low T₄ & TBG level with higher TSH level in thalassemia major patients. They related it with compensated subclinical primary hypothyroidism. They did not find any significant correlation between the hormonal parameters studied & chronological age or serum ferritin level in their transverse study. In contrast the longitudinal study showed significant correlation between pituitary thyroid axis dysfunction and siderosis. They postulated the presence of an individual different sensitivity of the gland to iron overload as a reason for different result in transverse and longitudinal study.

Spitz IM et al ²⁰ evaluated the thyroid function in 6 prepubertal male & 9 female thalassemic patients. 4 female cases were sexually immature [Group-1] with very low estradiol levels and the remainder had more advanced sexual development [Group-2]. Subjects were challenged with TRH and the response was compared to adult controls and a group of 15 males aged 13-18 years with constitutional delayed adolescence. They found all patients group and controls had normal T₃ & T₄ and T₃ resin uptake. When compared with adult controls or males with constitutional delayed adolescence, the male thalassemic patients had increased basal TSH with an exaggerated response to TRH. The more sexually mature female of Group-2 had also increased basal and stimulated TSH levels; though the sexually immature females of Group-1 had basal TSH and TSH response to TRH equivalent to female controls. In group-1 there were no changes in TSH response during administration of estradiol valerate for 3 months and conjugated

estrogen for 8 months. They concluded this high basal and stimulated TSH level in the males and Group-2 females were most likely due to subclinical primary hypothyroidism. The female thalassemia patients in their study failed to show an increased TSH response to TRH when estrogen administered. This pointed towards pituitary involvement.

Agarwal MB et al ²¹ studied 72 transfusion dependent iron loaded thalassemia patients for thyroid function tests by estimating circulating thyroid hormones [T₃, T₄] and basal TSH. The patients were also evaluated for liver function biochemically and iron overload by estimation of serum ferritin. They reported thyroid dysfunction in form of hypothyroidism in 19.4% of cases in their study with multitransfused thalassemia patients. They found three types of hypothyroidism. Group-1 58 cases [80. 6%] with normal T₃, T₄ & TSH levels, Group-2: 9 cases [12.5%] with compensated hypothyroidism with normal T₃, T₄ and raised TSH level. Group-3: 5 [6.9%] cases comprised of Decompensated hypothyroidism characterized by decreased T₄ & raised TSH. They had not found any correlation between impaired thyroid function with age, amount of blood transfused, liver dysfunction or degree of iron over load. They postulated interplay between chronic hypoxia, liver dysfunction and siderosis was responsible for thyroid damage.

Landau H et al ²² evaluated pituitary thyroid axis in thalassemia major patients in a cross sectional study & correlated it with iron over load. The course of thyroid disease was assessed in a 15 years longitudinal study. In Cross-sectional study: pituitary-thyroid axis function was examined in 37 patients (22 F, 15 M; aged 10-39 years, mean \pm SE = 21 \pm 1.4) out of a total of 43 who attended the Haematology and Endocrinology Clinics of Hadassah Hospital on a regular basis. The mean pretransfusion Hb level was 85 \pm 20 g/l, and all patients except one were treated with desferrioxamine (DF, mean \pm SE dose 20.2 \pm 2.6 mg/kg/day). Twenty-two had hypogonadotropic hypogonadism (HH). In Longitudinal study: 21

thalassaemia major patients were evaluated with TRH tests in 1976 and again in 1985. Fourteen of these and another eight were evaluated in both 1985 and 1991. In Cross-sectional study: No patient had any clinical signs or symptoms of hypothyroidism; however, one had abnormally low T4, borderline low FT4 and normal T3 levels associated with an exaggerated TSH response to TRH consistent with mild hypothyroidism. This patient did not have a previous TRH test, but serial basal determinations over 7 years revealed a progressive decrease in thyroid function. Thirty-six patients had thyroid hormone levels within the normal range. Nine of these (24.3%) had only an exaggerated TSH response to TRH whereas seven others (19%) also had borderline elevated basal TSH levels. TSH response to TRH was not correlated with age, serum ferritin or liver function tests (ALT or GGT). Longitudinal study: mean TSH response to TRH decreased ($\rho < 0.002$) and mean T3 levels increased ($P < 0.001$) between 1975 and 1985. These findings were probably related to the initiation of DF treatment. During the last 6 years of study, four patients with previously normal TSH responses to TRH developed elevated peak TSH levels. Mean T3 concentrations decreased and TSH response to TRH increased significantly ($\rho < 0.001$ for both). They concluded that in this patient group the thyroid pituitary axis was less sensitive than the gonadal axis to iron-induced damage; only one out of 37 patients developed mild uncompensated hypothyroidism. They also expressed that as opposed to the gonadal axis, the thyroid gland appeared to fail before the central components of the axis. The abnormal thyroid function might be reversible in the early stages. The progression was variable, and it might take years to progress from normal to uncompensated hypothyroidism.

al hader et al ²³ evaluated thyroid function in children with thalassaemia major. Basal thyroid function was assessed by serum thyroxine, tri-iodothyronine and thyroid-stimulating hormone levels in 90 patients 2-10 years old cases. Based on measured serum

ferritin levels, patients were classified into two groups: group (I) which included 63 patients with ferritin concentrations ranging from 300 to 7000 ng/ml (mild iron overload) and group (II) which included 27 patients with ferritin concentrations higher than 7000 ng/ml (severe iron overload). The results of thyroid function in both groups were compared with those of 50 control subjects. In-group (I), the mean concentrations of all measured hormones were not significantly different from those of the controls. In group (II), the mean concentrations of thyroxine and tri-iodothyronine decreased by 29 and 35 per cent ($p < 0.05$), respectively, and the mean concentration of thyroid-stimulating hormone showed a 2.6-fold increase ($p < 0.01$) in comparison with those of the controls. The data clearly demonstrated the occurrence of impaired thyroid function and its possible association with iron overload in a considerable proportion of transfusion-dependent beta-thalassaemic patients.

In an another study Thyroid function was evaluated in 20 patients aged 8-30 years who were suffering from homozygous beta-thalassaemia. All patients had been receiving frequent blood transfusions and treated for the resulting transfusional iron overload with intramuscular injections of Desferrioxamine. Total thyroxine (T4), T3-uptake, total triiodothyronine (T3), and reverse triiodothyronine (rT3) were measured. In addition a standard TRH stimulation test was performed and blood samples were checked for the presence of thyroid antibodies. It was found that total T4 was significantly lower in the patients than in the controls. Total T3 and rT3 levels were similar in both patients and controls and all patients were negative for thyroid antibodies. T3 uptake in the patients was also statistically different from the controls resulting in significantly lower free thyroxine index (FTI). Basal TSH values were not different from the controls but the TSH increase following TRH stimulation was significantly higher in the patients suggesting

together with the low total T4 and FTI, a state of compensated hypothyroidism²⁴.

Lividas DP et al ²⁵ performed thyroid and pituitary function tests using hypothalamic releasing factors in seven patients with thalassaemia and secondary haemosiderosis and in a control group of seven healthy subjects. The TSH level in the thalassaemic patients (18.07 ± 1.10 microU/ml) was higher than in the controls (1.01 ± 0.14 microU/ml, p less than 0.001). After TRH administration the TSH values increased less than in controls. Serum thyroxine and FT41 values were lower in the group of patients with thalassaemia (76.7 ± 7.8 nmol/l and 19.3 ± 2.2) compared to the controls (116.1 ± 6.9 nmol/l, P less than 0.005 and 38.6 ± 3.6 , p less than 0.001]. They expressed their opinion about presence of thyrotroph deficiency in the pituitary in the thalassaemia patients. They linked the latent hypothyroidism with coexisting hemosiderosis.

In an article Costing G et al ²⁶ showed presence of reduced thyroid hormone reserve in thalassaemia patients. They linked it with hemosiderosis induced endocrine gland damage.

In a study Serum concentrations of T4, T3, rT3, and TSH were measured by radioimmunoassay in 45 patients suffering from beta-thalassaemia. A TRH stimulation test was performed and the binding capacity of TBG and TBPA for T3 and T4 measured by reverse flow zone electrophoresis in a group of these patients. Mean T4 serum concentration was lower in thalassaemic patients than controls; T3, rT3, TSH levels, and the pituitary response to TRH were normal. TBPA binding capacity for thyroxine was greatly decreased, probably due to iron overload impairing the liver function. The decreased circulating total thyroxine explained by them due to the reduced TBPA capacity, serum free thyroid hormone concentration total thyroxine explained by them due to reduced TBPA capacity, serum free thyroid hormone concentration values being normal. It was concluded that thalassaemic children

were euthyroid, despite often having low-normal or subnormal thyroxine levels-This study was done by de- luca F etal ²⁷.

Senanayake MP etal ²⁹ had performed a cross sectional study to note thyroid function in thalassemia major. 33 patients with thalassemia major (19 males) aged 2 years 6 months to 23 years were studied. 21 healthy age and sex matched subjects from the same neighbourhood as the patients served as controls. Anthropometric measurements, skeletal maturity, serum ferritin and thyroid hormone levels were estimated. The height centiles and height standard deviation scores (SDS) were significantly lower in the patient group. Skeletal maturation was delayed by more than 1 year in 69% of patients. Undernutrition was not seen. The height SDS showed significant reduction with age ($r = -0.5$, 95% confidence limit -0.72 to -0.18) and with elevated serum ferritin levels ($r = -0.8$, 95% confidence limit = -0.9 to 0.62). Serum ferritin levels were elevated in the entire patient group with 70% being heavily iron overloaded (serum ferritin >7000 ng/ml). The thyroxine (T4) levels were within the normal range in all 33 patients. The TSH levels were normal in 32 patients. The patient too had a normal T4 level. The control group had TSH levels comparable with the patients. Hypothyroidism was not present in their iron overloaded thalassaemic patients. The thyroid hormone levels were similar in patients with mild and heavy iron overload. They concluded that routine surveillance for hypothyroidism was unnecessary in thalassaemia major. They opined about the need of investigation for other causes of delayed skeletal maturation and short stature.

Margo S etal ²⁹ studied 60 transfusion depended thalassemic patients by simultaneous measurement of thyroid hormones, basal TSH and TSH response to TRH aimed at evaluating the frequency of hypothyroidism & the relationship between hypothyroidism and compliance with treatment and iron overload in these patients. They found thyroid failure in 51.6% of thalassemia cases. They showed a correlation between impairment of thyroid function and duration of

chronic hypoxia, activities of various transaminases. They stressed on early evaluation of thyroid function in thalassemia patients for early detection of hypothyroidism and management of it.

A study was done to determine the level of testosterone, cortisol, luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), free thyroxine (T4), tri-iodothyronine (T3), growth hormone (GH), iron, ferritin, and haematological parameters in 44 beta-thalassaemia patients (21 = beta-thal. major, 23 beta-thal minor), 25 Hb S/beta zero-thalassaemia patients, and 50 normal controls with age range 2-15 years el Hazmi et al ³⁰. The iron endocrine status and haematological findings were evaluated, and the results were correlated and compared with age- and sex-matched controls. In comparison with controls the beta-thalassaemia-major and the Hb S/beta zero-thalassaemia patients had significantly higher level of plasma ferritin ($P < 0.01$) while the mean level of total haemoglobin was significantly lower. The level of LH, FSH, testosterone, and plasma cortisol were lower in both beta-thalassaemia-major and Hb S/beta zero-thalassaemia patients with a negative correlation with plasma ferritin level. Free T3 and T4 were raised, but the difference was not statistically significant. The data demonstrate the occurrence of impaired endocrine function in the beta-thalassaemia and Hb S/beta zero-thalassaemia patients.

Jain M et al ³¹ studied growth, skeletal maturation and thyroid function in 25 patients of thalassemia major in the age range of 5-17 years [Mean 10.3 ± 3.6 years] 25 age and sex mathed children who were not anemic served as controls. Thalassemia children in their study received multiple blood transfusion ranging from 36-350 units with mean 168.4 ± 98.9 [± 1 SD]. They found 28% of thalassemia cases below 5th percentile for height and 24% between 5th & 10th percentile. The height age retardation was more pronounced than bone age retardation. The mean total T₃, T₄ levels were significantly lower [$p < 0.001$] and mean serum TSH was

significantly high [$p < 0.005$] in patients with thalassemia major as compared to controls in their study. 5 patients had compensated hypothyroidism (\uparrow TSH, normal T_4 & T_3). 3 patients had uncompensated primary subclinical hypothyroidism (\uparrow TSH, \downarrow T_4 & normal T_3). 2 patients low T_4 with normal T_3 and TSH levels. They had not found any correlation between thyroid dysfunction and age, sex, hemoglobin level, country of origin but got higher amount of transfused iron load [unit\Kg] in patients with hypothyroidism [$p < 0.005$]. They concluded that hypothyroidism was unlikely to be the sole cause of growth retardation however it could've a permissive role. They suggested intense chelation therapy to prevent thyroid dysfunction.

In an Italian multicentric study ³² primary hypothyroidism was documented in 6.2% of thalassemia cases studied. They stressed on the need of regular endocrine evaluation in these patients for early detection of any associated endocrine complication to facilitate early management.

Masala A et al³³ evaluated the endocrine function in 20 prepubertal homozygous β thalassemia patients treated with frequent transfusion and chelation therapy. FSH, LH, PRL, TSH secretion was evaluated by LRH, TRH testing. No statistically significant difference was found between FSH, LH, PRL GH secretion in the patients and normal subjects. There was a relatively high incidence of [35%] of primary thyroid impairment since 1 patient had primary hypothyroidism and 6 others had evidence of subclinical hypothyroidism as manifested by increased response to TRH. However they had not found any significant correlation between either serum ferritin levels, total blood transfusion received, and thyroid function.

Borgna – Pignetti et al ³⁴ evaluated growth and sexual maturation in 250 adolescents with thalassemia major. The pre transfusion hemoglobin was not less than 9.5 gm\dl in their study with desferrioxamine administered for last 7-10 years. They found

37% of the patients were two standard deviation below the mean for the normal height; after age 14 years the percentage was 62% for males and 35% for females. 83% of males and 75% of females had delayed skeletal maturation. Complete lack of pubescence changes was present in 38% of females and 67% of males aged 12-18 years. A multiple regression analysis of the indicators of pubertal development with age, age at first transfusion, age at splenectomy, number of transfusion, serum transaminases and ferritin, and duration and intensity of chelation therapy failed to identify the factors responsible for variation observed by them.

Gulathi R et al ³⁵ prospectively evaluated 84 thalassemia patients for growth, growth hormone, IGF-1, thyroid hormone, cortisol and glucose tolerance over one year. They found height standard deviation score of patients more than 8 years was $[-2.2 \pm 1.5]$ against National Center for Health Statistics reference] significantly lower than that of normal controls $[-1.0 \pm 0.7, \rho < 0.001]$. 51% of the patients had GH deficiency. Dynamic testing of 54 children revealed 33% had at least one endocrine deficiency other than short stature. They concluded that thalassemia children in developing countries might be at risk for endocrine deficiencies at younger ages.

Oerter KE et al ³⁶ performed extensive endocrine evaluation in thalassemia major patients which included spontaneous and stimulated level of gonadotrophins, GH, thyroid hormone & adrenal hormone in 17 patients. They found all of them with at least one endocrine abnormality. Abnormality of Hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis was most common. Six patients failed either the provocative GH test or had mean spontaneous GH less than $1 \mu\text{g/L}$. 4 patients who failed provocative tests had growth velocities more than 2SD below for mean bone age. The patients had evidence of primary hypothyroidism. They concluded that all patients with hemochromatosis need periodic careful endocrine evaluation.

De Santis V et al³⁷ done a retrospective study on growth in a group of thalassemia who had completed puberty spontaneously and attained adult height. They grouped 64 patients in 3 groups according to transfusion regimen and chelation therapy. Group A with 16 patients who were transfused regularly at low hemoglobin levels [8.5 gm\dl] from an early age and started subcutaneous chelation therapy during adolescence. Group B consisted of 19 patients who were transfused regularly at high hemoglobin levels [10 gm\dl] from an early age and started chelation therapy during childhood. Group C patients [29] were transfused at high hemoglobin levels [10.5 gm\dl] from very early years of life with mean 2 years. Standard auxological measurements were made at 3 monthly interval till adult height reached. They found Group A male and female patients did not grow significantly better than those in group B. Group C patients grew no faster than those who started chelation therapy late in childhood. The majority of Group A & B patients had reduced spurt in height at puberty. In addition a reduced sitting height due to spinal growth abnormality found. An inverse correlation between sitting height and serum ferritin was observed in Group A patients [$r = -0.55, \rho < 0.05$], whereas there was a direct relationship in group B patients [$r = 0.42, \rho < 0.05$]. They concluded that an ideal therapeutic regime was yet to be found with decreased iron toxicity & optimum growth. They recommended that the growth of the thalassemia patients should be monitored regularly at every follow up visit to detect early changes in growth for appropriate investigation and treatment.

Caruso - Nicholetti et al³⁸ studied 476 patients with thalassemia major in 2-36 age group. Auxological data [standing height, Sitting height, sub ischial leg length,] hematological data [age at first transfusion , age of starting chelation, ferritin] and information regarding presence of endocrine abnormality , bone lesion were sought and analyzed. They found 18% of thalassemia patients with short stature. 14% with disproportionate upper and

lower segment and a short trunk despite normal stature in 40% of patients. They opined the short stature due to a spinal growth impairment, which started in infancy and aggravated progressively. Other factors like siderosis or desferrioxamine therapy might have some influence in it.

Saka N et al ³⁹ studied growth and sexual development in 54 thalassemia major patients aged 2.7-21.3 years. Mean pre transfusion hemoglobin was 7.8 ± 0.7 gm/dl. Maximum patients were on desferrioxamine therapy. Age of starting therapy was 6.8 ± 3.9 years. Mean standard deviation score [SDS] for height, weight and sitting height were significantly lower [$p < 0.001$] than control cases of similar ages. Height deficiency exceeded -2 SD in 18 patients and bone delay observed [>2 SD below mean] in 36 patients. Height SDS were negatively correlated with chronological age, age of onset of chelation and serum ferritin level [$p < 0.001$]. They opined for regular chelation therapy to overcome the growth impairment and delayed puberty.

Perignon F et al ⁴⁰ studied 31 thalassemia patients, 28 of them had regular blood transfusion since 3.7 ± 3.6 years. Iron chelation started before 10 years in 9 patients, after 10 years in 15 cases and not done in the rest. GH, Thyroid, Cortisol, PTH [Parathyroid Hormone] studied. The GH peak after stimulation was normal but plasma somatomedin was low and did not increase at puberty. 6 patients had peripheral hypothyroidism. The mean final height they found -1.3 ± 1.0 SD in boys and -1.3 ± 0.9 SD in girls. They concluded hypothyroidism as one of the important endocrine abnormality found in thalassemia patients.

Tienboon P et al ⁴¹ prospectively studied 115 non-splenectomized β thalassemia patients who had not received chelation therapy. Most children in their study had abnormal weight for age [WAZ] & height for age [HAZ] score. Though female patients had lower WAZ [$p < 0.0001$] and HAZ [$p < 0.02$] compared to

males, mild to moderate degree of wasting was also normal in those patients. Severe weight deficits were more prevalent in the youngest [$p < 0.01$] and severe stunting in the older [$p < 0.01$] children. Nearly all children were $< 50^{\text{th}}$ percentile for both weight for age & height for age, and majority were below 5^{th} percentile. Pre transfusion hemoglobin was invariably associated with anthropometric measurement. They concluded that in addition to linear growth failure varying degree of wasting was also typical in thalassemia. The weight deficit occurred at an early age and preceded deficits in linear growth. Abnormal growth was not due to chelation therapy and was inconsistently associated with degree of anemia. They concluded that in the growth failure associated general malnutrition played a significant role. Associated endocrinopathies like hypogonadism, hypothyroidism, hypoparathyroidism add to the complication.

Low LC⁴² expressed that iron overload, toxic effects of desferrioxamine or the endocrinopathies like GH deficiency or primary hypothyroidism contributes to growth failure in thalassemia patients. Abnormal body proportion with truncal shortening are commonly seen and could be due to the disease itself, iron toxicity, delay in puberty or toxic effects of desferrioxamine. The absence of pubertal growth spurt during spontaneous or induced puberty is detrimental to the achievement of normal adult height. Low serum IGF-1 and normal GH reserve in short thalassemia patients imply a state of relative GH resistance exists. The rise in IGF-1 and improvement in growth with GH therapy indicated that the deficiency is partial. Although the results of short-term GH therapy are encouraging, the impact of treatment on final height of non-GH deficient short thalassaemic children remains uncertain. Multiple endocrinopathies, including hypogonadism, hypothyroidism and diabetes mellitus, occur mainly in older patients who tend to have high serum ferritin levels. Prognosis for survival is greatly improved if the serum ferritin is kept below 2000 micrograms/l by regular

chelation. Chelation therapy initiated early before the accumulation of a significant iron burden or dosages of desferrioxamine in excess of 50 mg/kg/day should be avoided. Serum ferritin should be checked regularly and the "toxicity index" should be used to monitor chelation therapy. In cases of delayed puberty, sexual development should be induced at an appropriate age.

Grundy RG et al ⁴³ investigated the extent of endocrine dysfunction in a group of 18 thalassemia patients with 11 well chelated cases. Assessment of growth and puberty showed a wide variation in height SD scores with five patients having significantly short stature. Most patients were progressing through puberty normally with the exception of two boys with marked pubertal delay. The most prominent finding was that growth hormone responses to glucagon stimulation were significantly impaired in all of the patients with iron overload. Basal endocrine assessment showed primary hypothyroidism in two patients aged 16.8 and 12.9 years with plasma thyroxine-concentrations of 86 and 59 nmol/l (normal range 65-165 nmol/l) and plasma thyroid stimulating hormone 10.2 and 30.3 mU/l (normal range 0.5-5 mU/l). One patient had diabetes mellitus. These results show that even when ideal management was sought a significant amount of endocrine damage occurs; surveillance of these patients is thus essential.

Jensen CE et al ⁴⁴ investigated incidence of endocrine dysfunction in relation to the genotype of β thalassemia. In addition the relationship between serum ferritin and endocrinopathies studied. They found 64% of patients had at least 1 endocrine disorder and 40% had multiple endocrinopathies. The most common was hypogonadotropic hypogonadism. They had found a positive correlation between serum ferritin concentration and presence of thyroid or parathyroid dysfunction.

Yesilipek MA et al ⁴⁵ studied growth and endocrine disturbances in 71 thalassemia major over 3 years. Twenty-three patients (32.4%) were below the third centile for height. Growth

retardation was more pronounced in-patients 10 years of age and up according to height and weight standard deviation scores (SDS). Delay in bone age was found in almost all patients, and 74.5% of their patients over 12 years of age had not yet entered puberty. These results showed that growth and endocrine disturbances have significant negative effects in the quality of life of thalassemic patients. They pointed for more detailed studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted on thalassemia patients who were being admitted in the indoor of the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Medical College, Kolkata for Blood transfusion. Total fifty [50] thalassemia cases with twenty-five [25] cases each of male and female were taken. The control group also comprised of fifty [50] subjects with equal number of male & female patients. The case and control group was age and sex matched. The biochemical analysis was done by the Department of Green Biochemistry, Medical College Hospital, Kolkata.

SUBJECTS:

The thalassemia cases were diagnosed cases of thalassemia between five [5] to twelve [12] years. All patients received multiple blood transfusion. The ward "Multitransfused" here indicates patients who had received more than or equal to twenty [20] units of packed red cell transfusion. Each unit comprised of 15 [fifteen] milliliter of packed cell transfusion per Kilogram of body weight approximately. No patient had received any form of iron chelation therapy. The cases were selected at random who had fulfilled the above criteria.

The control group subjects were taken from out patients Department of Pediatrics Medicine, Medical College, Kolkata. They attended the OPD for unrelated minor illness. They were also between 5 to 12 years. No control subject had any clinical symptom or sign of thyroid dysfunction. The case & control group were age and sex matched. Controls were otherwise healthy & selected at random.

Exclusion criteria for cases:

- Undiagnosed cases of chronic hemolytic anemia.
- Patients below 5 years or above 12 years.

- Cases which received blood transfusion within last 15 days of sample collection.
- Any case with history of iron chelation therapy.

Exclusion criteria for controls:

- ❖ Any subject with clinically evident thyroid dysfunction or goiter or liver dysfunction
- ❖ Children who received blood transfusion in past for any reason.
- ❖ Any subject with pallor or hepatosplenomegaly.

The cases and controls were examined clinically in details. The height & weight percentile was calculated with charts of NCHS [National Center for Health Statistics] standards ¹¹ [Proforma attached]. The hepatomegaly was expressed as enlargement of liver in centimeters below right costal margin along right midclavicular line. The splenomegaly was described as enlargement of spleen in centimeters from left costal margin along the splenic axis. The nature and purpose of the study were carefully explained to the parents of the cases and controls prior to obtain their consent. The thyroid function will be evaluated clinically and by estimation of T4 and TSH. The liver function will be evaluated clinically and by estimation of SGPT, Bilirubin and Albumin.

Sample Collection & estimation:

5 ml of clotted blood and 2 ml of EDTA blood sample were taken from both cases and controls by needle puncture of peripheral veins. The clotted blood was centrifused @ 1500 rpm. The serum thus obtained was taken in two test tubes. Serum bilirubin, SGPT and albumin were estimated on the same day from serum of one test tube. The serum of the other test tube was stored at - 20° Centigrade. The biochemical assay for serum Thyroxine, TSH and Ferritin was done later in batches of 25 samples at convenient time. Controls for samples were taken in each biochemical estimation.

Hemoglobin was estimated on the same day by automated analyzer from the EDTA sample.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The average values were expressed as Mean \pm 1 Standard Deviation [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. The samples with more than 30 subjects [cases and controls] were compared by applying Z test. Samples comprising less than 30 subjects were evaluated by unpaired T test. Height and weight percentile proportions in case & controls were analyzed by proportional analysis with application of Z test. ρ Value less than 0.05 was taken as significant with 95% confidence limit and ρ value less than 0.01 was regarded highly significant with 99% confidence limit ^{8,9}.

INSTRUMENT AND REAGENTS:

The biochemical tests were performed in MICROLAB-100 & MICROLAB-200 [E Merck, Germany]. It was a semi autoanalyzer working on photometric principle utilizing different field tests.

Hemoglobin was measured by cyano method.

Thyroxine [T₄] was analyzed in Enzyme immunoassay (Magnetic Solid Phage) method using T₄-Serozyme Kit [Biodate Company, Code-12821504]. Quantitative estimation of total Thyroxine done.

TSH was analysed by Immunoenzymetric assay [Magnetic Solid Phage]-Quantitative analysis. Kit used- TSH Serozyme [Biochem Immune System Code-12731504].

Bilirubin was measured by Merckotest kit code 110333.0001 using Jendrasik & Grof method.

Serum Albumin was measured by Ecoline [-Merck Code-1118275] kit by photometric determination.

SGPT was estimated by Ecoline-ALAT [Merck -code-1117661.0001] using reference method of International Federation of Clinical Chemistry {IFCC}.

Ferritin was measured by ELISA technique.

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Proforma of History & examination in this study

Reference No: Case\Control _____ Date: _____

Name: _____ Age: _____ Sex: _____

Address: _____

Socioeconomic status of the parents: _____

Age of receiving first blood transfusion: _____

Total number of blood units transfused: _____

[Approximately]

Symptoms _____ of _____ Thyroid
dysfunction: _____

Clinical Examination:

Facies: _____ Height: _____ cms. Weight: _____ Kg

Pallor: _____ Icterus: _____ Pulse: _____ \min

Neck vein: _____ NeckGlands _____

Blood Pressure: _____ mm Hg Respiratory

rate: _____ \min Skin\Pigmentation: _____

Tanner Staging: _____

Liver: _____ cms Spleen: _____ cms

Thyroid Gland: _____

Cardiovascularsystem: _____

Nervous System _____

Biochemical Investigations

Investigation:	Result	Investigation	Result
Hemoglobin:		Serum T ₄	
Serum bilirubin:		Serum TSH:	
Serum SGPT:		Serum ferritin	
Serum Albumin:			

Reference level for different biochemical parameters:

- Thyroxine [T₄] : 5.5 –12.5 µg\dl [5-12 years] ⁶
- Thyroid Stimulating Hormone[TSH]: 0.7-6.4 m IU\L [5-12 years] ⁶
- Bilirubin [Total]: 0.1-0.5 mg\dl [After one month of Age] ¹⁰
- Albumin: 4-5.3 gm\dl [5-19 years] ⁶
- SGPT: 5-45 U\L [1-19 years] ⁶
- Ferritin ; 7-140 ηg\ml [6 month- 15 years] ⁶
- Hemoglobin: 11.5-14.5 gm\dl [6-12 years] ⁶

RESULTS WITH ANALYSIS

50 multitransfused thalassemia patients (25 male & 25 female) were studied with similar number of control subjects in each sex group. 46 cases [92%] were from low socioeconomic families with income less than 1500 Rs per month. 4cases[8%] from families with monthly income between 2000-2500 Rs. The control group had also 42 subects [84%] from families with monthly income less than 1500Rs. Per month. 8 subjects [16%] in control group had a family income between 2000-2500 Rs per month.

Thalassemia patients were growth retarded. Height & weight percentile both were reduced. 48 cases [96%] were below 3rd percentile in height & 39 cases below 3rd percentile in weight. In comparison number of controls with height & weight less than 3rd percentile were 26 [52%] & 22 [44%] respectively. Moreover none of the thalassemia patients were above 50th percentile in height & weight. The reduction in height & weight was statistically significant with $\rho < 0.001$ for height & $\rho < 0.01$ when compared with controls. (Diagram: 1)

All children with thalassemia had moderate to severe degree of pallor. Mean pretansfusional hemoglobin was 4.31 gm\dl with SD 1.64. 5 patients had clinical sign of heart failure at the time of examination. Blood pressure was within normal limit for that age and sex and a soft systolic functional murmer was heard in a number of patients along left sternal border. The patients probably tolerated the effect of chronic hypoxia with low hemoglobin level. Low incidence of heart failure inspite of severe anemia was probably due to the development of tolerance to chronic hypoxia.

The age for starting blood transfusion was 1.49 ± 1.41 years [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$] -{ μ =Average & σ =Standard Deviation}. Average amount of blood transfused to each child was 69.18 ± 45.56 units [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Amongst 50 cases 44% had got 20-50 blood unit, 44% had 51-100

units, 8% had 101-150 units & 4% had received more than 151 units of blood [Diagram:2].

Clinically jaundice seen in 21 cases [42%]. Most of these cases had mild icteric tinge in bulber conjunctiva. Serum bilirubin level was 2.72 ± 2.75 mg\dl [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. The elevated bilirubin was mostly unconjugated. Only one patient had bilirubin 19.4 mg\dl with conjugated bilirubin 13.9 mg\dl. Subsequently he was found to be suffering from hepatitis b infection probably acquired through repeated blood transfusion [Diagram: 3]. Serum bilirubin level in the control group was 0.54 ± 0.2 mg\dl. The difference was statistically significant [$\rho < 0.0001$].

No patient had any symptom or sign of thyroid dysfunction. On palpation thyroid gland was normal, no goiter present. No obvious depigmentation noticed in the thalassemia patients.

Liver enlarged in all cases. Avarage hepatomegaly was 5.08 ± 4.62 [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$] centimeter below right costal margin in right mid clavicular line. Avarage spenomegaly was 8.87 ± 4.62 centimeters [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$] below left costal margin along its axis. Three patients had their splenectomy done.

13 patients [26%] of age group 9-12 years who were expected to show pubertal changes had their external genitalia in pre adolescent stage {TannerStage:1}.

Biochemical analysis of liver function revealed serum SGPT elevated in 36 cases [72%]. Average serum SGPT level was 104.24 ± 136.88 U\L [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. The value of SGPT for control group was 26.32 ± 11.98 U\L [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. The difference was statistically significant at ρ value < 0.0001 [Chart: 6C]. Serum albumin level was below normal 26 cases [52%]. Level of albumin in the thalassemia cases was 3.94 ± 0.48 gm\dl [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Albumin value for the control group was 4.28 ± 0.45 gm\dl. Thalassemia patients had significant reduction in their albumin level [$\rho < 0.03$]. From this results it can be said that

significant hepatic functional derangement seen in the Multitransfused thalassemia patients [Diagram:4, Chart:6].

All patients had markedly elevated serum ferritin levels indicating iron overload. Only 5 cases [10%] had ferritin below 1000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$. 7 cases [14%] with ferritin between 1000-2000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$, 6% had ferritin between 2000-3000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$. 11 cases [22%] with ferritin level within 3000—4000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$, 6% each with ferritin between 4000-5000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ & 5000-6000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$. 7 cases [14%] were in serum ferritin 7000-8000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ range, The number of cases between 8000-9000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ was 3 {6%}, & above 9000 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ was 3 [6%]. Average serum ferritin level was 4916.02 ± 2809.97 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. The results of the control group was 50.68 ± 13.05 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. This difference was highly significant statistically with $\rho < 0.0000001$ {Diagram: 5}.

Thyroid dysfunction in form of hypothyroidism seen in 32 patients [64%]. Serum T_4 in the Multitransfused thalassemia patients was 5.71 ± 1.97 $\mu\text{g}\backslash\text{dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Values for the control group was 7.73 ± 1.86 $\mu\text{g}\backslash\text{dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Serum TSH level in the patients was 6.69 ± 6.22 mIU\backslashL [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$] whereas TSH in the control subjects was 3.88 ± 2.36 mIU\backslashL [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Mean T_4 was significantly low [$\rho < 0.000001$] & mean TSH was significantly higher with $\rho < 0.01$ in the thalassemic patients. [Diagram:6].

Thalassemia patients had been divided according to thyroid function into four [4] groups.

Group-1: 18 cases [36%] -Normal thyroid function. Normal T_4 & TSH level. The thyroxine level in this group was 7.08 ± 1.52 $\mu\text{g}\backslash\text{dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. TSH level was 4.19 ± 1.66 mIU\backslashL [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$].

Group-2: 11 cases [22%]- Compensated hypothyroidism. Normal T_4 & \uparrow TSH level. Thyroxine level was 6.78 ± 1.43 $\mu\text{g}\backslash\text{dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$].

1 σ]. Average TSH level was 12.98 ± 10.39 mIU/L [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$].

Group-3A: 8 cases [16%]. Decompensated hypothyroidism. \downarrow T₄ TSH level. The thyroxine level in this group was 3.48 ± 0.55 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. TSH level was 9.08 ± 1.59 mIU/L [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$].

Group-3B: 13 cases [26%]- Patients having decompensated hypothyroidism with Pituitary dysfunction. Serum Thyroxine reduced but TSH normal or Even reduced. T₄ level was 4.27 ± 1.11 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. TSH level was 3.38 ± 1.46 mIU/L [$\mu \pm 1\sigma$]. Normally reduced thyroxine level is accompanied by elevated TSH level. In presence of pituitary dysfunction patient may not be able to mount a raising response to declined T₄.

Comparison of thyroid function in different groups revealed TSH level was significantly low in Group-2 with respect to Group-1 [$\rho < 0.01$] but difference in Thyroxine level was not significant. There was statistically significant low Thyroxine level [$\rho < 0.01$] and high TSH [$\rho < 0.001$] in Group -3A when compared with Group-1. Group-3B had low value of T₄ [$\rho < 0.001$] but normal level of TSH when analyzed with respect to Group-1. [Diagram-6,7]

These four group of thalassemia patients based on varied thyroid function, were analyzed for different parameters like age of starting blood transfusion, total number of blood unit transfused, height & weight percentile, iron overload and liver function to find out any correlation between these parameters.

Age from which blood transfusion started for different Groups was as follows. Group-1: 1.57 ± 1.50 years, Group-2: 1.97 ± 1.38 years, Group-3A: 1.29 ± 1.41 years, & Group-3B: 1.09 ± 1.31 years. Results expressed as $\mu \pm 1\sigma$. There was no statistically significant difference found in the age of onset of transfusion in different Groups.

Amount of blood transfused in units for various Groups were: Group-1: 55.66 ± 26.93 units, Group-2: 76.55 ± 49.2 units, Group-3A: 108.75 ± 73.57 units and 57.31 ± 27.41 units in Group-3B cases. Results expressed as mean ± 1 standard deviation. In general there were no significant difference in amount of blood transfused in different groups except Group 3A patients received more blood when compared with Group-1 with $\rho < 0.02$ [Diagram-14].

Analysis of difference in height percentile in different Groups showed 17 cases [94.44%] in group-1, 10 cases [90.9%] in Group-2, 8 [100%] patients in Group 3A and 13[100%] cases in Group -3B were below 3rd percentile in their height with respect to that age & sex. The proportion of thalassemia cases below 3rd percentile in height in Group 2 , Group 3A & Group-3B were statistically not different in comparison with Group-1 [$\rho > 0.05$] [Diagram-9].

Weight of thalassemia patients below third percentile in different Group as follows. Group-1: 16cases[88.88%], Group-2: 10 patients[90.9%], Group-3A: 6cases [75%], Group-3B: 7 cases[53.84%]. The proportion of cases below 3rd percentile in Group-2 & Group-3A were not significantly different with Group-1 patients [$\rho > 0.05$]. Group -3B cases had significantly less number of patients when compared with Group-1 cases [$\rho < 0.05$]. It indicates that Decompensated hypothyroidism patients with pituitary dysfunction had more cases above 3rd percentile when tallied with euthyroid thalassemia cases. This significant data needs further evaluation [Diagram-8].

Splenomegaly in various Groups showed as mean \pm standard deviation as follows. Group-1: 6.5 ± 4.49 cms, Group-2: 9 ± 4.11 cms, Group-3A: 12.83 ± 1.41 cms, Group-3B: 8.76 ± 3.35 cms. Spleen size was not statistically different in Group-2, 3A, 3B when compared with Group-1[Diagram-15].

Average hepatomegaly in different Groups varied. It was 3.89 ± 1.68 in Group-1, 6.09 ± 3.33 in Group-2, 5.25 ± 2.49 in Group-3A & 5.76 ± 2.16 in Group-3B. Data presented as $\mu \pm 1 \sigma$. Statistical analysis showed liver was more enlarged in Group-2 [$\rho < 0.05$] & in Group -3B [$\rho < 0.02$] in comparison with Group- 1. In contrast Group-3A patients did not showed any difference in hepatomegaly with Group-1. This varied liver enlargement was not enough to draw a conclusion.[Diagram-16].

Clinically icterus present in 7 cases [38.88 %] in Group-1, 5 cases [45.45%] in Group-2, 3 cases [37.5 %] in Group-3A & 5 patients [38.46%] in group 3B thalassemic patients [Diagram-10].

Pretransfusional hemoglobin level varied in different groups. Group-1 had pretransfusional hemoglobin 4.89 ± 1.63 gm\dl whereas group-2 had 5.09 ± 1.71 gm\dl, Group-3A had 3.3 ± 1.07 gm\dl & Group-3B had 3.45 ± 1.21 gm\dl. Data expressed as $\mu \pm 1 \sigma$. There was no significant difference in pretransfusional hemoglobin in Group-1 & Group-2. Group-3A & Group-3B patients had significantly low hemoglobin level when compared with Group-1 cases at ρ value < 0.05 & < 0.02 respectively. So it can be said that more anemia present in more deranged thyroid function patients in this study. Chronic hypoxia arising out of chronic anemia may have some role in causing hypothyroidism [Diagram-13]

Serum SGPT level in different Groups was as followed. 104.06 ± 145.4 U\L in Group-1; 139.54 ± 222.12 U\L in Group-2 ; 50.78 ± 48.81 U\L in Group-3A and 81.84 ± 47.61 U\L in Group-3B

[$\mu \pm 1 \sigma$]. Comparison of bilirubin & SGPT levels in different Groups based on thyroid function did not revealed any statistically significant difference. So liver dysfunction did not varied significantly in different Groups [Diagram-12].

Serum albumin level was below normal in 7 cases[38 .88 %] in Group-1, 6 cases [54.54%] in Group-2 ; 5 patients [62.5 %] in Group-3A & 5 cases [38.46 %] in Group-3B. Average albumin level in as gm\dl in Groups 1,2,3A,3B were 4.09 ± 0.41 ; 3.9 ± 0.53 ; 3.7 ± 0.56 ; 3.9 ± 0.46 { $\mu \pm 1\sigma$ } respectively. Serum albumin was significantly low in Group-2 when compared with Group-1 [p 0.05] but no significant difference found in albumin level of Group 3A & Group-3B with Group1[Diagram-11].

All four groups based on different thyroid function had very high serum ferritin level signifying heavy iron load. Serum ferritin in various Groups as followed. 4541.66 ± 2574.2 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ in Group-1; 4773.72 ± 3021.22 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ in Group-2; 3692.55 ± 2647.54 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ in Group-3A & 5026.92 ± 3222.35 $\eta\text{g}\backslash\text{ml}$ in Group-3B. No statistically significant difference found in serum ferritin level of Group -2,3A & 3B when compared with Group-1 patients with normal thyroid function [Diagram-17].

Diagram:1

Color Code: Green=Cases Blue=controls
 1=Height ;2=weight

Diagram:1 --- Showing Comparison of patients and controls below 3rd Percentile in Height and weight [n=50]

Diagram :2

1=20-50 Units of Blood Transfused
 2=51-100 Units of Blood Transfused
 3=101-150 Units of Blood Transfused
 4=>151 Units of Blood Transfused

Diagram:2- Showing average amount of Blood transfused in Thalassemia Patients
 [n=50]

Diagram :3

Color Code:Blue[1] With Jaundice , Merun[2]: Without Jaundice

Diagram 3: Showing Incidence of Jaundice in Thalassemia Cases [n=50]

Diagram:4

1=SGPT Level; 2=Serum Albumin Level

Blue=Abnormal Values: Raised SGPT & Decresed Albumin Level

Pink=Normal Values

Diagram :4 Showing abnormal SGPT & Albumin level in thalassemia Cases [n=50]

Diagram :5

X-Axis= Level of Serum Ferritin In Thousand ng\ml

Diagram :5 Showing Percent of cases according to serum Ferritin Level [n=50]

Diagram:6

1=Hypothyroidism

2=Normal Thyroid Function

Diagram :6 Showing Thyroid function in Thalassemia Cases [n=50]

Diagram:7

- 1=Group -1** Patients [n₁=18] normal Thyroid Function(Normal T₄ And Normal TSH)
- 2=Group—2** Patients [n₂=11] Compensated Hypothyroidism(Normal T₄ & ↑TSH)
- 3=Group-3A** Patients [n₃=8] decompensated Hypothyroidism (T₄& ↑TSH)
- 4=Group-3B** Patients [n₄=13] Decompensated Hypothyroidism with pituitary involvement(↓ T₄ & Normal or ↓ TSH)

Diagram:7 Showing different categories of Thyroid Function in thalassemia patients

[n=50]

Diagram:8

- 1=Group-1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ; 4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:8 Showing percentage of thalassemic patients with weight below 3rd centile

Diagram:9

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:9 Showing percentages of cases below 3rd percentile of height in different groups

Diagram:10

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:10 Showing percentages of patients with jaundice in different groups according to thyroid function.

Diagram:11

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:11 Showing percentage of patients with serum albumin level below normal

Diagram:12

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:12 Showing percentage of patients with serum SGPT level above normal

Diagram:13

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8]
4=Group3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:13 Showing Average Hemoglobin level of patients in different groups

Diagram:14

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:14 Showing Average number of blood unit transfused in different group of patients

DiagramNo:15

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:15 Showing Average enlargement of spleen in centimeter in different group patients

Diagram:16

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

Diagram:15 Showing Average enlargement of Liver in centimeter in different group of Patients according to thyroid function.

Diagram:17

1=Group -1[n₁=18] ; 2=Group—2 [n₂=11]; 3=Group-3A [n₃=8] ;
4=Group-3B[n₄=13]

of **Diagram:15** Showing Average serum ferritin level in different group
Patients according to thyroid function.

DISCUSSION

Thalassemia patients are virtually dependent on regular packed cell transfusion for their survival. They do suffer from growth retardation. Retardation of both height & weight seen in thalassemia patients. Multiple blood transfusion invariably leads to deposition of iron in various organ and tissues. This secondary hemochromatosis damages the pituitary –thyroid axis contributing to delayed physical and sexual growth. Costin G et al ²⁶ histologically demonstrated iron deposition in endocrine glands as a consequence of iron over load by regular transfusion therapy. Thyroid gland is a very important gland to maintain normal physiology of body. Damage due to iron is an important though rare cause of thyroid dysfunction ^{46,47}. Siderosis induced damage at various level of hypothalamic-pituitary-peripheral endocrine organ is a well-known entity in thalassemia patients.

In the present study reduction of height seen in multitransfused thalassemia cases. 48 cases [96%] were below 3rd percentile in their height. The reduction in height was significant statistically when compared with control group. There was no significant difference in the proportion of thalassemia cases below 3rd percentile in their height found amongst different groups' based on thyroid function. 39 cases [78%] below 3rd percentile in their weight, which was significantly, higher than control group. Cases with compensated hypothyroidism & decompensated hypothyroidism were not different in their weight retardation when matched with thalassemia patients with normal thyroid function. However thalasseemics with decompensated hypothyroidism along with pituitary involvement were less retarded in weight when compared with cases with normal thyroid function. This needs further evaluation.

So it can be said from this study that growth retardation seen in thalassemia patients but role of hypothyroidism couldn't be correlated statistically. Agarwal et al²¹ got 79.3% of euthyroid and 85.7% of hypothyroid patients below 3rd percentile. They had not found any significant difference between these two groups. Pignetti et al³⁴ showed 37% of thalassemia cases below two standard deviation from mean in height & weight in a group of 250 patients. Jain et al³¹ in their study found 28% of cases below 5th percentile in height. Height age was significantly less than chronological age. They did not find any correlation between growth retardation and anemia, transfused iron load. They opined against the direct cause and effect relationship between thyroid function and growth retardation. Madeddu et al¹⁸ showed presence of growth retardation in their study in several patients in their study during first year of life and the retardation affected all the thalassemia patients when they reached puberty. This retardation was not correlated with hypothyroidism in their study. Senanayake et al²⁹ also found delayed skeletal maturation and lower height percentile in thalassemia cases.

Tanner staging is done usually above 9 years age and this study had 13 cases in 9-12 years age group. Pubertal delay found in all cases. Siderosis & chronic hypoxia induced damage of the hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis may be the cause of this pubertal delay.

In spite of improved prognosis of thalassemia patients with more intense transfusion therapy, chelation, splenectomy the percentage of patients with growth retardation still remained high and documented by various authors^{48,49,50,51}. In the present study severity of growth retardation seen in the transfusion dependent thalassemia patients couldn't be correlated with number of blood units transfused, thyroid function, degree of anemia, liver dysfunction and iron overload. The growth retardation seen in chronic anemias like thalassemia, is probably due to impaired

oxygen delivery to tissue, increased work of cardiovascular system, increased energy demand for enhanced erythropoiesis and associated malnutrition.

Amount of blood transfused does not seem to affect significantly growth, thyroid function, and liver function and iron overload. When thalassemia cases with normal thyroid function were compared with patients having thyroid dysfunction no statistically significant difference found in amount of blood transfused in different groups. Similar type of finding was reported by Agarwal et al ²¹ in their study. However Jain et al ³¹ documented significantly higher number of blood transfusion \ Kg body weight & transfusion \ year received by the thalassemia patients with hypothyroidism than euthyroid thalassemia cases. They postulated that thyroid hypofunction might be related with iron over load and related iron toxicity. They had not performed any biochemical test to see the iron load like serum ferritin which had reduced the importance of this finding.

Average pretransfusional hemoglobin level of thalassemia cases in this study was 4.31 gm \ dl which was significantly lower than control. When pretransfusional hemoglobin was compared in different groups it was found that hemoglobin in Group 3A & 3B was significantly lower than hemoglobin level in Group 1. Chronic hypoxia might have some role in thyroid dysfunction. Agarwal et al ²¹ did not find any significant correlation between hemoglobin and thyroid function.

Significant hepatosplenomegaly was present in almost all thalassemia patients. Mean hepatomegaly was 3.89 cms and mean splenomegaly was 6.5 cms. There was no difference found in the splenomegaly of cases with different thyroid function. Liver enlargement varied in different groups but it was not sufficient to draw a conclusion.

Hepatic function was deranged in the multitransfused thalassemia patients. 21 cases [42%] had icterus clinically. Both serum bilirubin and SGPT were elevated. Serum albumin was low in the case group. The difference in liver function between case & control was statistically significant. When liver function was compared in different groups based on thyroid function, no significant difference found. The Hepatic functional derangement was not correlated to serum ferritin level and thyroid dysfunction. Gangeni et al ¹⁶ also noted SGPT level raised three times normal in their study with thalassemia patients. They found a correlation between liver dysfunction and age of the patients, ferritin level. Although Agarwal et al ²¹ had not found any significant correlation between liver function and thyroid dysfunction & ferritin level.

Serum ferritin level was raised in all patients with thalassemia. The mean ferritin level was 4619.02 ng/ml. That was significantly elevated in comparison with the control group. The difference in ferritin level in the thalassemia patients grouped according to thyroid function was not significant statistically. So the severity of thyroid dysfunction was not correlated with serum ferritin level. Agarwal et al ²¹ also reported similar finding in their study.

In the present study 32 cases [64%] had some form of hypothyroidism. 11 cases [22%] had a state of compensated hypothyroidism - normal T₄ and ↑TSH. 8 cases [16%] had decompensated hypothyroidism- ↓ T₄ & ↑ TSH. 13 thalassemia patients [26%] had decompensated hypothyroidism with pituitary involvement. The mean T level was significantly lower and mean TSH level was significantly higher in thalassemia patients when compared with control group.

The cases were grouped according to thyroid function to find out correlation with different parameters. The comparison showed that there was no significant correlation of thyroid function with age at starting blood transfusion, total number of blood unit transfused,

hepatic dysfunction, and iron overload [serum ferritin]. Though pre-transfusion hemoglobin was significantly lower in cases with more severe hypothyroidism. Chronic hypoxia could be an etiological factor for this difference. No children had any symptom or sign related with thyroid dysfunction. This hypothyroidism often goes undetected because less attention is paid to it.

Agarwal et al²¹ found 20% incidence of hypothyroidism in their study. They had not found any correlation between thyroid function, liver function and ferritin level. Margo et al²⁹ showed 50% cases with thyroid failure in thalassemia patients. They correlated the thyroid dysfunction with duration of chronic hypoxia and activity of transaminases. An Italian study documented 62% incidence of hypothyroidism. It stressed on regular evaluation of thyroid function in thalassemia patients for early detection of hypothyroidism³². Madeddu et al¹⁸, Spitz IM et al²⁰ also observed hypothyroidism with ↓ T₄ & ↑ TSH. Phenekos C et al²⁴ found compensated hypothyroidism in form of ↓ T₃, ↓ T₄ normal TSH with increased response to TRH stimulation. Livida DP et al¹² reported ↑ TSH level in transfusion dependent thalassemia patients. They postulated about pituitary deficiency of thyrotrophs & correlated with coexisting siderosis. These findings were supported by Cavallo L et al¹⁹ who showed ↓ T₃ & ↓ T₄ along with ↑ TSH in their study. They correlated it with compensated primary hypothyroidism.

Jain M et al³¹ found ↓ T₃ & ↓ T₄ with ↑ TSH in their study. Al Hader A et al²³ demonstrated occurrence of impaired thyroid function and possible association with iron over load in multitransfused thalassemia patients.

The occurrence of hypothyroidism in thalassemia patients was contradicted by Senanayake et al²⁹. They showed normal T₃ & T₄ in thal cases in their study. They opined against routine surveillance of thyroid function in thalassemia patients. de Luca et al²⁷ normal T₃ & TSH level with low thyroxine in thalassemia cases.

They concluded that thalassemia patients were euthyroid despite presence of normal or subnormal thyroxine level. Normal thyroid function was also reported by other workers ^{52,53}.

From this discussion it is evident that hypothyroidism is present in a significant number of transfusion dependent thalassemia patients. Iron overload had been implicated as an etiological factor for hypothyroidism but no correlation could be found between iron overload and thyroid & hepatic dysfunction in this study. Probably a combination of chronic hypoxia , hepatic functional derangement with iron overload results in thyroid dysfunction. This finding strengthen the importance of regular thyroid function evaluation in multitransfused thalassemia patients for its early detection and management, a view supported by Agarwal etal²¹.

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